

SOCIALRES ENERGY INNOVATION FRAMEWORK: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EXISTING BUSINESS MODELS FOR RES COOPERATIVE, AGGREGATORS AND CROWDFUNDERS

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ABSTRACT

The energy sector is facing a transition phase in which the development of renewable energies and a greater social participation will be two fundamental measures of this transition. Besides, the liberalization of energy markets permits new actors to be involved and to develop original business models. Based on the ongoing research activities in the frame of the H2020 European project SocialRES, aiming to close non-technological research gaps in the energy sector, this paper contributes to identify how social and environmental standpoints impact different business model in this sector. The aim is to present a framework to analyse the business models within the energy sector and to apply this framework to the analysis of three types of businesses associated with social innovation in the renewable energy sector: Cooperatives, Aggregators and Crowdfunding platforms. The results contribute to energy entrepreneurship and identify innovative attributes applied either in the supply side or in the demand side.

Fig. 1 SocialRES geographical and social innovation coverage

Keywords: Business Model, Social innovation, Crowdfunding, Aggregation, Cooperatives

1 AIM AND APPROACH USED

This paper to be presented at the EUPVSEC2021 aims to characterize different business model archetypes existing in the energy sector and how social and environmental standpoints impact these business models. This research work has been performed in the frame of the H2020 European project SocialRES. The aim of SocialRES is to close non-technological research gaps that impede the widespread uptake of social innovation

business and service models in the European energy sector.

The SocialRES consortium brings together thirteen partners who have been chosen specifically for their expertise and experience to ensure the successful implementation of the novel research proposed in this project and to guarantee a widespread geographical coverage (Fig.1). The SocialRES project partners are briefly described in the following paragraph.

1. WIP – Renewable Energies (WIP), based in Germany, the project coordinator.
2. ESTIA Institute of Technology (ESTIA), based in France, with extensive experience in research aspect of social innovation and innovative business models.
3. CARTIF, energy expert based in Spain.
4. Bodensee-Stiftung - Lake Constance Foundation (LCF), based in Germany, as networking and innovation expert and providers of case studies for RES cooperatives.
5. Adelphi, policy think tank based in Germany.
6. Fondazione iCons (ICONS), communication, dissemination and exploitation expert based in Italy.
7. Trinity College Dublin (TCD), University based in Ireland, with extensive experience in behavioural and energy economics, and consumer engagement.
8. I-ENER, RES cooperative based in France, involved in social innovation research projects.
9. EnergEtica, RES cooperative based in Spain.
10. Power Parity, RES cooperative and crowdfunding platform based in Portugal.
11. Abundance, RES crowdfunding platform based in United Kingdom.
12. REGEA, RES crowdfunding platform based in Croatia.
13. Tractebel, RES aggregator based in Romania.

Social innovation projects address broad social issues, in this case the clean energy transition, while also driving business forward.

Three types of businesses have been considered associated with social innovation in the renewable energy sector: Cooperatives, Aggregators and Crowdfunding platforms.

On the one hand, this paper aims to present a framework to analyse the business models within the energy sector. On the other hand, and based on this framework, this paper analyses different business model archetypes existing in the energy sector.

2 SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

Cooperatives, Aggregators and Crowdfunding platforms are associated with social innovation in the renewable energy sector. These businesses *facilitate an increase in energy democracy by increasing the number of local (decentralised) clean energy projects and allowing the consumer to take a more active role.*

Based on the attributes examined in the scientific literature and aiming an accurate framework to analyse the business models within the energy sector, a specific model is first presented in the paper. This conceptual framework is suitable for new entrepreneurial business model design and is being used in the frame of the SocialRES project to develop original business models merging Cooperatives, Aggregators and Crowdfunding platforms activities. Moreover, this framework can be used by researchers as a key unit of analysis in the energy transition studies.

Then, this study analyses different business model archetypes existing in the energy sector based on the scientific literature and a detailed analysis of 9 cases of social innovations implemented by crowdfunding platforms, cooperatives, and aggregators in 7 EU countries (Fig.1). Indeed, energy entrepreneurs are promoting clean energy technologies and creating innovative business models that associate commercial benefits and

sustainability aspects. However, the process of finding out the appropriate business models poses challenges to new market actors, researchers, and policy makers. In this regard, *the paper will explore how new entrepreneurs within the domains of Cooperatives, Aggregators and Crowdfunding platforms create and capture value from innovative business models based on existing technologies.*

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The results will be presented following the conceptual framework based on the three priorities for the future European energy system (security, affordability and sustainability) as well as other attributes applied either in the supply side or in the demand side. In the supply side, generation viewpoint is considered. This includes flexible generation means that will play an important role in the energy system. Therefore, in order to identify the value propositions related to the supply flexibility, a specific subdivision has been considered. This value proposition includes specific business models as well as special means as storage systems.

The demand side is related to the consumption part. Energy can be used to fulfil several functions which are usually classified into heat functions, mobility functions and specific electricity usages. In this case also, a specific subdivision has been considered: The demand flexibility or the Demand Response.

Lastly, a particular attribute has been considered to include the *specific role of the Energy Communities*. These communities are created by different partners but mainly by the customers. Indeed, in this model, the role of the customer is highlighted because of the fact that customers can be members of the energy community and can realise specific activities that are not usually done in standard companies. From an energy community point of view, the customer can be an active stakeholder of the organisation in the management area or financial area (the customer is also an investor).

The results can assist new market actors and stakeholders during their early development stage to construct new business models in the energy market. The findings contribute to energy entrepreneurship and identifies innovative attributes to make the business model approach a key driver for the energy transition.

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